

Adverse soils tolerance

MR375—A salt-tolerant rice suitable for coastal saline soils

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About 4,500 ha of rice land along the coasts of Karnataka are flooded by seawater every kharif. The Agricultural Research Station (ARS) at Ankola, on the sea coast of North Kanara district, is well suited for research on coastal saline soils and on varietal improvement for salty areas. The station's soils are acidic, generally high in exchangeable sodium and hydrogen, and low in calcium content. The varieties B146 and K12 are successfully grown in wetland soils of this region during kharif. B146 was selected at Ankola from a natural bulk population of the variety Bilekagga; K12 is from Karekagga. B146 does well in less severely saline soils. K12 can withstand higher salt concentrations and is suitable for low-lying wetlands. Both are tall indica varieties with coarse grains, prominent awns, and red kernels. Although their grain quality is poor their yields are fairly high in wetland conditions.

To improve its grain quality and plant

type, K12 was crossed with IR8 in 1970. The progeny, now stabilized, are being tested in yield trials to determine their suitability for inland and coastal saline soils, and in adverse soils at the UAS experimental station at Hiriyur and at Ankola. Eighteen selected K12/IR8 lines (designated "MR") and 10 other standard salt-tolerant varieties were tested in wetland soils at the Ankola ARS. The entries were grown in a randomized block design with 4 replications, fertilized at 40-40-40 kg NPK/ha. The net plot size per entry was 4 m², spaced at 20 × 15 cm and seeded at 75 kg/ha.

MR375 yielded highest, 1.8 t/ha, followed by Dasal and Gettu (1.5 t/ha) (see table). MR375, a semitall variety with stiff straw and medium-slender grains, matures in about 125 days. Its yields did not differ significantly at the 1% level from those of Dasal and Gettu, the standard salt-tolerant varieties. The next best culture, C7 (1.3 t/ha), is a semidwarf with fine grains, similar to those of Sona, and tight panicles. In experiments at the Hiriyur ARS in inland saline soils, C7 was tolerant of inland salinity, although its yields were inconsistent. The performance of the salt-tolerant SR26B in wetland at the

Results of salt tolerance variety trial at the Agricultural Research Station, Ankola, Karnataka, India, 1978 wet season.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Maturity (days)
MR261	0.6	78	146	134
MR339	0.6	63	103	114
MR340	0.9	61	123	115
MR341	0.6	62	133	114
MR342	0.9	65	136	114
MR375	1.8*	93	113	123
MR343	1.2	99	146	115
MR338	0.8	70	123	114
MR346	0.9	73	99	123
K142	0.4	79	146	117
MR358	1.0	66	136	114
MR359	1.2*	84	146	139
MR361	0.7	111	160	140
MR362	0.8	75	120	117
MR363	0.7	91	126	132
K125	1.2*	66	99	112
MR376	0.8	67	126	111
MR377	0.4	57	89	123
Dasal	1.5*	86	113	133
Gettu	1.5*	90	118	133
Madhu	1.2*	74	116	113
IR2070-4-14	0.3	70	120	118
C7	1.3	71	106	118
Mangala	0.4	66	140	98
IET2254	1.0	65	113	123
Arya	0.7	113	146	124
F test	**			
CD (0.05)	0.4			
CV %	28.6			

* = differs significantly (P=0.05) from the highest yielding check (Arya); ** = significant at 1% Level; CD = critical difference at 5% level.

Ankola ARS was not encouraging. With suitable agronomic practices MR375 should yield at least 2 t/ha in wetland. ■

Several nematodes, in addition to the ufra nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* (which causes the most damage to deepwater rice), were extracted from the roots and soil. Until this study, those sites of infestation had been studied in less detail than the aerial parts of the deepwater plant. The following types of nematodes were found:

Type	Sites (%) with infestation
<i>Meloidogyne graminicola</i>	30
<i>Hirschmanniella oryzae</i>	52
<i>Tylenchorhynchus martini</i>	16

Deep water

Root and soil parasitic nematodes of deepwater rice areas in Bangladesh

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Parasitic nematodes were surveyed in nine deepwater rice areas of Bangladesh

in collaboration with members of the ODM-funded Deepwater Rice Pest Management Team, BRRI. Samples of soil and water, and of plant material, were collected at 65 sites randomly selected from farmers' fields from 19 June to 9 August 1978. Nematodes were extracted from the culms, panicles, roots, soil, and floodwater, and identified at IRRI.

Seventy-two percent of the sites were infested with plant parasitic nematodes.